

FORMATION OF COMPETENCE IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS AND IMPROVEMENT OF QUALITY EFFICIENCY IS THE DEMAND OF THE TIMES

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Abstract. *This article will be devoted to improving the formation of competence in students and improving the quality and effectiveness of education in the course of the educational system.*

Keywords: *quality of education, great educator Yan Amos Komensky, competency, competence psychology, creativity, professional competence, modern pedtechnology, modern teacher.*

INTRODUCTION

A healthy and well-rounded generation in our country in the conditions of globalization education, creative and intellectual potential of young people upgrade and can fully meet the requirements of the present time, each to ensure that they become well-rounded individuals is the main goal of our development today. In our country, since the first years of independence, the education system has been developing, and the head of our country has paid great attention to ensuring that our youth acquire modern knowledge and skills in accordance with world standards, mature into physically and spiritually mature people, realize their abilities and talents, intellectual potential, Effective work is being done to cultivate the feelings of loyalty and self-sacrifice in their hearts.

It is known that the education system plays a very important role in the development of society. In the decree of the President of February 7, 2017 "On the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", a number of priority tasks for the development of the social sphere, in particular, the spheres of education and science, were defined. The development of our society requires the introduction of a new innovative education system for students to plan their future and develop their professional skills. In order to apply the new pedagogical technology to the educational process, it is necessary to create its scientific and practical mechanism.

The main task of increasing the effectiveness of the teaching process in educational institutions is to make students work for the development of our society, to be creative in order to acquire knowledge, and to constantly improve their knowledge. It is necessary to teach students not to be satisfied with explaining new topics in the course of the lesson, but to increase their demands for learning, to read more books, to work according to plans, to be able to gather thoughts, to be able to direct them to a specific goal, to be disciplined, and to be able to correctly evaluate the achieved results.

If the students study well during the lesson, the higher the quality and efficiency of the teaching, the more well organized their independent study and learning is. Environment and upbringing are important in the comprehensive formation of students. Beruni emphasizes that three things are important in human perfection. This is the heredity, environment and education that modern pedagogy also acknowledge.

The goal. Education in our country experience of reforms shows that the most socially important qualities of a person: sociability, responsibility, initiative, creative approach to business, decision-making, etc. today's skills development is relevant today. The formation of such qualities in future specialists will allow them to carry out effective activities in the future. The problem is with increasing the responsibility of speech for related professions is to teach high-quality effective communication, the ability to master words, to solve professional problems using words. From our research our goal is pedagogy in the process of teaching, technology is necessary for the development of communicative competence of students of higher education institutions determination of pedagogical conditions, theoretical justification.

The object of research is technical higher education pedagogy of students of institutions the process of developing communicative competence in learning subjects.

Achieving the quality and effectiveness of the education system in all higher education institutions should be the main goal of the national education system of any country. In order to raise the quality and efficiency of education in educational systems to a higher level, it is appropriate to improve the organization of educational methods, modern pedagogical technologies, and new teaching methods applied to the educational process, as well as targeted use of foreign technologies.

The fact that not only students, but also teachers and pedagogues are theoretically and practically ready for the implementation of foreign technologies in the educational process ensures the further improvement of the quality of education. It is possible to determine the level of development of our society and the changes in the educational system, that in order to prepare young people as qualified specialists who are mature in all respects, who can assess the situation in the educational process in time, and who can make the right decision in any situation, it is necessary to form their characteristics right now.

The main tasks of teachers and pedagogues today are to implement all the innovations in the educational system based on the essence of all studied subjects and to implement them in the educational process. In order to achieve the organization of high-quality training of students in the educational system, it is necessary to apply new methods and forms of teaching introduced in several types of education in the system.

It is known that during the period of the former Soviet regime, textbooks were used in the schools of Uzbekistan, which were subordinated to the ideology of communism and were written only by pedagogues-scientists of the capital Moscow and translated in Uzbekistan. As a result, our young generation became deprived of the national pedagogy, national spirituality and cultural treasure inherited from our ancestors. Therefore, in the process of reforms in pedagogy today, it will be correct to abandon "Soviet pedagogy", create theoretical and practical foundations of national pedagogy, and apply its principles and methods in pedagogical activity. If we look at the early periods of independence and compare it with the new changes in the education system today, unprecedented changes are causing the emergence of the following professions: managers, programmers, engineers, nanotechnologists, tourism specialists, logisticians, transporters, image makers, anesthesiologists and other similar specialties. and the overall need for them is also increasing.

In the development of professional competence in the educational process, it is important to use modern pedagogical technologies of education. The task of modern education today is related to the development of students' competence in professional, legal, national, spiritual-

educational, ideological and cultural terms. The concepts of competence and competence are mutually exclusive appear as categories with a specific meaning of the competence approach. In many literatures, there are different opinions about the interdependence of these concepts, and definitions with different bases are given to it. By competence we understand that a person's personal quality is formed as a knowledge-based, intellectual and socio-professional description of a person. Competencies require not to be satisfied with existing traditional ideas in determining the purpose of education, that is, not to be limited to viewing it as a system in which knowledge, skills and competences are formed.

Competence is the ability of a person to find an opportunity in terms of his profession to solve his life and professional problems. "Competence is the ability to use knowledge, skills and personal qualities for successful activity in a certain field," said Professor N. Muslimov, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences. they are always ready. The founder of the psychology of competence, the English psychologist J. Raven, based on the concept that "competency is a set of competencies", emphasized their versatility. Competence, which J. Raven interpreted as the characteristics and abilities that allow people to achieve important personal and professional goals, regardless of what they are, is not developed innately in education and independent professional and social activities. Pedagogical conditions are necessary for the formation of professional competences of teachers and the effective development of ideological and pedagogical competences. The glorification of the teaching profession is considered by scientists as one of the main means of increasing the effectiveness of education. It is possible to understand the pedagogical conditions for the development of competence in teachers, the organization of necessary and important measures for the process to be at a high level. Analysts of the World Economic Forum (World Economic Forum) as the main competencies of the future are solving complex tasks, thinking, creativity (from the Latin "creato" - creation, creation), people management, interpersonal skills, emotional intelligence, reasoning and decision-making. , customer orientation, negotiation, and cognitive (an individual's independent thought process). have distinguished such as flexibility. All of the listed competencies refer to adaptive skills, and at the same time they serve to develop students' ideological-ideological competence. In order to form the competence of students, it is necessary to develop their leadership qualities mainly through creative work competitions, legal literacy days, Olympiads, discussions, quizzes, creative evenings, traditional sports and cultural events, clubs, and excursions. It is important to develop a methodology for determining the level of quality and efficiency by analyzing and summarizing the results obtained for the development of students' competence. To determine the level of effectiveness of the pedagogical education system aimed at the development of competence, it is necessary to carry out experimental work.

Science teachers should have all-round knowledge, skills and qualifications in educating students with a high level of professional competence. In addition, science teachers should constantly search for themselves in order to be knowledgeable, experienced, skilled educators, passionate and selfless in their field, creatively approach their work, and be able to interest students in their subject. In order to achieve this, teachers of special subjects and professional teachers should be able to properly plan the content of their work, properly apply teaching technologies to the educational process, know information technologies, and effectively use modern pedtechnologies in the training process. What should a modern teacher be like?

The main thing is that the teacher should skillfully and qualitatively impart all the knowledge he has to the student he is teaching, and the student should try to master and learn all

the necessary knowledge. our scientists are conducting their scientific research work and studying it in every way. Today, it is the demand of the times to make future teachers fully mature and competent, to educate them, to study the experiences and technologies of developed countries, to adapt them to the conditions and to effectively use them, to prepare specialists who can meet the requirements of the time.

Research methods. Our research in accordance with the goals and objectives, we to confirm the proposed hypothesis we used the following research methods:

- general scientific methods: philosophical theoretical analysis, psychological, pedagogical, methodological literature, studied issues regulatory documents, analysis of pedagogical experience, comparative analysis, classification, content analysis, modeling.
- empirical methods: survey, test conducting, in the process of diagnosing the level of development of communicative competence, the products of student activity analysis, expert evaluation method, observation, pedagogical experience (identification and formation).

CONCLUSION

As a result of the study the following conclusions were formed:

1. The development of communicative competence in the process of training future specialists in the higher education system also depends on the level of communicative competence of teachers.

2. Choosing a pedagogical management style

It is determined by the flexibility and variability of the pedagogical communication technique, it is intrinsically dependent on the specific conditions of the students, their age and individual characteristics, and their activities.

3. Purposeful formation of communicative competence of future professionals who have fluent speech skills, who can independently and correctly choose the style of professional communication and activity, actively using the generalized psychological and pedagogical knowledge in their work, is essential.

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